

2. Adult scarabaeid beetles chew the base of rice stems just above the roots.

by chewing the base of the stem just above the roots (Fig. 2). Although the Indian beetle usually damages rice seedlings, the pest attacks dryland rice at all stages in Bangladesh. If plants are attacked after flowering, whitehead-like damage occurs. In early stages of an attack, rows of dead hills are observed near levees. Whole fields are later damaged. Beetles are found in sandy or sandy loam soils.

Although no control experiment has been conducted, aldrin, dieldrin, heptachlor, carbofuran, fenitrothion, and malathion have been tentatively recommended for control. If irrigation water is available, flooding the fields for a few days is also successful.

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Granular insecticides for control of major rice insects in Thailand

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Insecticide plays a major role in rice insect control in Thailand. Insecticide importation was 10,045 t in 1980 and has increased 2-3 times during the last 6 years. About 20% of the insecticide was used for rice. Monocrotophos has been

used for many years as a foliar spray but is now widely distributed in local markets in granular form. This study evaluated the effectiveness of monocrotophos and other granular insecticides for rice insect control.

In a greenhouse test monocrotophos effectively controlled brown planthopper (BPH) and gall midge (GM) as compared to carbofuran (see table). Diazinon also caused high BPH mortality and was moderately effective for GM. In a field experiment, contradictory results were found. Monocrotophos and dia-

zinon did not control GM but carbofuran, followed by chlorpyrifos and quinalphos, was effective. Although stem borer incidence was low, carbofuran-treated plants had fewest deadhearts. Diazinon-treated plants had more deadhearts than the untreated check at 60 days after transplanting. Carbofuran treatment produced the highest grain yield. Diazinon and monocrotophos treatments did not produce yields significantly different from the untreated check. Reasons for contradictory greenhouse and field results for monocroto-

Effect of granular insecticides on rice gall midge, brown planthopper (BPH), and stem borers in Thailand, 1981^a

Treatment	Greenhouse		Field				
	Silver shoots (%)	BPH mortality (%)	Silvershoots (%)		Deadhearts (%)		Grain yield (t/ha)
	20 DI	4 DAT	30 DT	60 DT	30 DT	60 DT	
Carbofuran	1 a	94 a	4 a	1 a	0.9 a	0.4 a	
Chlorpyrifos	52 cd	—	6 ab	5 ab	2.6 a	5.1 ab	1.91 b
Quinalphos	26 bc	—	4 a	13 b	1.0 a	4.7 ab	1.87 b
Diazinon	20 b	100 a	15 bc	49 c	2.4 a	12.7 c	1.24 cd
Cartap	—	—	21 cd	63 d	0.6 a	5.4 ab	1.10 d
Monocrotophos	8 ab	98 a	26 d	50 c	1.0 a	7.6 bc	1.21 cd
Untreated control	65 d	14 b	22 d	41 c	1.9 a	6.1 ab	1.34 c

^aGreenhouse tests were conducted at the Rice Protection Research Center, Bangkok. The field trial was at Chumpae Rice Experiment Station, Khon-kaen. Insecticides (1 kg ai/ha) were applied to 20-day-old rice planted in clay pots for greenhouse trial, and 3 times at 15, 30, and 45 DT in the field trial. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different ($P = 0.05$). DI = days after infestation. DAT = days after treatment. DT = days after transplanting.

phos and diazinon are unknown. Past experience with diazinon for BPH control also yielded different greenhouse

and field trial results. Diazinon has always given poor BPH control in the field. Whether or not monocrotophos is

an effective BPH control in the field needs further assessment. *h*

Orthoptera pests of transplanted rice in hills of Uttar Pradesh

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Grasshoppers, crickets, and a mole cricket have been found to cause heavy damage to transplanted rice in the hills of Uttar Pradesh. Damage is most severe in the nursery. Sometimes, the leaves of seedlings are completely eaten, leaving only the midrib and stalks. Before infesting a rice crop, nymphs and adults generally feed on grasses growing on rice field bunds or on sorghum and

Orthopteran species causing rice seedling damage in the Uttar Pradesh hills, India.

Family	Species	Intensity
Acrididae	<i>Acrida exaltata</i> (Walk.)	Moderate
	<i>Catantops pinguis innotabilis</i>	Low
	<i>Hieroglyphus banian</i> (F.)	High
	<i>Oxya fuscovittata</i> (Marschall)	High
Pyrgomorphidae	<i>Atractomorpha crenulata</i> (F.)	High
	<i>Chrotogonus</i> sp.	Moderate
Gryllidae	<i>Trigonidium cicindeloides</i> (Serville)	Moderate
	<i>Teleogryllus occipitalis</i> (Serville)	Low
Tettigoniidae	<i>Euconocephalus</i> sp.	Moderate
Gryllotalpidae	<i>Gryllotalpa</i> sp.	Low

millet.

Ten orthopteran pests have been identified from 4 years' observations and the intensity of damage determined (see

table).

Identification of species was confirmed by the Commonwealth Institute of Entomology, London. *h*

Soil and crop management

Upland rice varietal reactions to aluminum toxicity on an Oxisol in Central Brazil

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Brazil is the world's largest upland rice producer. About 70% of this production comes from the central region (22% of the country's area) which is a tropical savanna locally called *cerrado*. Aluminum toxicity causes serious yield reductions in this region. A CNPAF research program was initiated to identify rice cultivars tolerant of aluminum toxicity in the field.

Soil at the experimental site had pH 5.2, 0.52 ppm available phosphorus, 0.25 meq exchangeable Ca + Mg/100 g soil, 15 ppm available potassium, and 0.55 meq exchangeable aluminum/100 g soil.

Either no lime was applied to plots, or lime was applied at 3 t/ha. All plots were fertilized with 50 kg N/ha, 44 kg P/ha, 50 kg K/ha, and 5 kg Zn/ha.

Varietal evaluation at high and low levels of aluminum, Goiás, Brazil.

$$\text{Lime response} = \frac{\text{yield in limed plot} - \text{yield in unlimed plot}}{\text{Al saturation of limed soil} - \text{Al saturation of unlimed soil}}$$

Al saturation values were measured at flowering.

They were plowed and disked 50 days before sowing and lime was broadcast and mixed with a rototiller. Fertilizers

were broadcast before sowing and disked into the top 15 to 20 cm soil. Seeds of 142 varieties were planted in